

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ELECTRONIC PRESCRIPTION SYSTEM IN THE UNIFIED HEALTHCARE INFORMATION SPACE

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Abstract

An electronic prescription is a digital analogue of a paper prescription and is available not only to the treating doctor and patient, but also to the pharmacist. The work proposes an electronic prescription system as one of the components of a unified medical information system for healthcare. Some foreign experiences on the use of electronic prescriptions are presented. The use of an electronic prescription is available for use both on personal computers and as a mobile application. The main advantages are the storage and availability of doctor's prescriptions in digital format, the ability to quickly search for a prescribed drug in the pharmacy network, statistics and forecasting of drug purchases.

Keywords: electronic prescription, medical information system, digitalization of healthcare, mobile application in healthcare.

One of the stages of the transition to digitalization of healthcare is the development and use of an electronic prescription. An electronic prescription (ER) is a digital equivalent of a paper prescription that is created, stored, and transmitted using a medical health information system [3]. The use of ER requires entering data about the patient and prescribed medications into a centralized data bank of the system for medical records with the formation of the necessary document. Many ER systems, based on data, generate a QR - code that confirms the legality of the prescription, with which you can purchase the medicine or get it at the pharmacy for free. The ER system creates the prerequisites for more effective and safe treatment:

- eliminates unreadability or misinterpretation of recipes;
- allows you to see all medications prescribed to the patient;
- makes it possible to avoid erroneously indicated dangerous dosages and unwanted interactions between drugs, etc.;
- allows you to avoid unnecessary visits to the clinic just to renew your prescription;
- eliminates duplication of drug dispensing for one patient;
- excludes the forgery of preferential prescriptions, as well as prescriptions for the dispensing of medicines that are subject to quantitative registration;
- saves the doctor's time on writing prescriptions, especially taking into account the possibility of extending the validity of an electronic prescription.

Many countries have already switched to an electronic system for issuing medical documents. The unified digital system involves not only treating doctors and pharmacists, but also insurance companies and regulatory organizations. The Scandinavian countries were

the first to implement the ER system. In Sweden, such projects began to appear in the 80s of the last century [1]. Gradually, digital prescriptions were integrated into the electronic health record system. A single database has been formed where data on all prescribed drugs is stored throughout the entire validity period of the prescription. In this case, the patient does not have access to the electronic prescription itself, but can get medicine at any pharmacy by simply confirming his identity [2].

The European Union plans to create a unified international e-health system, where all citizens will be able to receive medications using electronic prescriptions from a pharmacy in any state belonging to the EU [1].

In England, ER became relevant in 2018, and in 2019 digital prescriptions were introduced throughout the country. Today, patients have access to two service options: a paper prescription with a barcode, which allows them to obtain the medication at any pharmacy included in the system, and an electronic prescription, which the doctor direct to a specific pharmacy.

In the United States, the implementation of a unified electronic records system began in 2009, when the country's government adopted the law on the implementation of information technology in medicine (HITECH). By 2012, according to a report by the Office of National Health Coordination, about 48% of medical institutions switched to electronic document management. Today, electronic prescriptions are issued by 85% of doctors and served by 99% of all pharmacies in the United States. In New York and some other states, the use of ER is mandatory[5].

In Azerbaijan, the transition to electronic prescriptions began in 2023 with use in the Baku City Narcological Dispensary as a pilot project. The goal of this

project was to eliminate paperwork and serve citizens in a digital format. This will prevent the illegal sale of drugs that cannot be sold without a prescription and ensure transparency in this area. It was planned that such a mechanism would help monitor the circulation of drugs, reduce the number of counterfeit documents, as well as control the treatment of patients for certain disease profiles and eliminate the uncontrolled dispensing of drugs from pharmacies.

The electronic prescription system is part of a single information space that covers clinics, hospitals and pharmacies (Fig. 1). This is a system for synchronizing

information between medical institutions and pharmacies, which allows you to effectively monitor the circulation of medicines. Thus, when writing a prescription for a drug, the doctor and patient are provided with information about its availability in pharmacies, which simplifies the process of interaction between doctors, patients and pharmacists. Remote receipt of an electronic prescription is especially convenient for patients with chronic diseases. They will no longer have to visit a doctor to renew their prescription for the necessary drug, but will only come for mandatory examinations.

Fig. 1. Functional scheme of a medical information system

Issuance of an electronic prescription includes the following:

- a patient's visit or online request to a doctor – therapist or specialist;
- the doctor diagnosis, prescribes treatment, selects suitable drugs from the system help;
- the doctor enters all the necessary information, draws up a prescription and certifies it with a personal electronic signature;
- the finished prescription, along with patient data, information on dosage and regimen taking medication, is entered into the database;
- if the patient is entitled to the exemption, this is also reflected in the document;
- if necessary, the doctor gives the patient a paper duplicate.

To date, there is no regulatory document that would abolish paper prescriptions. Therefore, at the test stage, doctors are forced to do double work: even for those who have an electronic card, they duplicate the prescription on paper. For now, this is a necessity: firstly, it insures against possible failures in the system, and secondly, it gives the patient the right to choose a pharmacy[8].

The “Electronic Prescription” system is a unified register for registration and management of prescriptions for medical drugs prescribed to citizens in public and private medical institutions in Azerbaijan. The “Electronic Prescription” system can be used by all persons receiving services under compulsory health insurance, as well as those belonging to the preferential category, as well as citizens receiving services under private health insurance, as well as uninsured citizens.

The patient can access the electronic prescription either on the government services website <https://reseptim.az> or through the “Reseptim” mobile application. In your personal account on the website and in the application, all prescriptions made by the doctor are displayed. A digital prescription is available not only to the treating doctor and patient, but also to the pharmacist.

The very friendly and intuitive interface of this solution, available on both personal computers and mobile devices, allows the doctor to write prescriptions based on the international classification of diseases and medicines officially registered in the country (Fig. 2).

The user logs into the system through the government identification system [3] and can see all prescriptions issued to him in a simple structured and readable form. The system allows you to write prescriptions

based on the active substance, which gives the buyer freedom of choice when purchasing medicines. You can download the mobile application on the website <https://reseptim.az> and in the AppStore and Google Play applications.

Through the “Reseptim” mobile application, you can search for a pharmacy where the desired drug is available, and also place an order. The built-in verifica-

tion service simplifies the process of obtaining medicine, thanks to which information from the unified register of a medical organization is compared with the information in the prescription. The system automatically transfers the online prescription to the pharmacy for service, and the patient only needs to go to the desired address and show the pharmacist a QR- code on the screen of their mobile device.

Fig.2

The electronic prescription is entered into the system and stored in the patient's electronic record. When a patient contacts a pharmacy, the dispensing of the prescribed drug is registered in the pharmacy's accounting system, and the prescription acquires the “served” status. If the drug is not available in the pharmacy, the prescription is placed on deferred service, the corresponding status is entered in the registry, and the bearer of the prescription is informed about the expected date of receipt of the drug.

Integration of this register with the register of control over the movement of medicines, as well as its integration with the database of payment machines will strengthen control over operations carried out during the sale of medicines, including preventing the distribution of counterfeit and unregistered drugs.

Having prescribed a medicine to a patient, the attending physician fills out an electronic prescription form, rules for taking the drug and the validity period of the prescription, which is transmitted via secure communication channels to the data processing center. In the general database, the doctor also sees the entire history of his prescriptions and can see whether the patient actually purchased the medicine.

It should be noted that this register is a source of medical information for citizens, which will subsequently be combined with the “Citizen's Medical Digital Twin” system to ensure the integrity of the citizen's medical data in his digital profile [6, 7]. The Electronic Prescription system is one of the main initiatives towards improving the quality of medical care and digitalization at the early stage of healthcare transformation [1].

In conclusion, we indicate the main advantages of the electronic prescription system:

1. All doctor's prescriptions are stored in digital format - no problems reading the name and dosage. Information about the duration and regimen of taking medications is always available online.

2. Saving the doctor's time for working with the patient. An electronic prescription can be renewed remotely (for patients with chronic diseases).

3. An electronic prescription cannot be lost, torn or damaged. Due to the need to understand the doctor's handwriting, the pharmacist does not make mistakes in the name and dosage when selling the medicine.

4. The ability to quickly search for a prescribed drug in a pharmacy chain by location.

5. The risk of purchasing a counterfeit drug using an electronic prescription is minimized.

6. The attending physician, and, if necessary, his colleagues, can immediately see all prescriptions made in electronic form that the patient purchased with a prescription. Also, the generated prescription is compared with the patient's other prescriptions to eliminate a possible conflict of medications.

7. The electronic prescription system helps to select drugs depending on their availability in pharmacies. Online, the doctor is shown the range of medications in pharmacies, which allows him to quickly replace the medicine with its equivalent if the required drug is not available in the pharmacy.

8. Forecasting the purchase of medicines, planning and working with suppliers. Real statistics about prescribed drugs.

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